

Strategies to get more student enrolled in Universities in Nigeria

Ademola Ilesanmi, Taiwo Ilesanmi, Gbadesere Tolu

The world population review [1] states that Nigeria has a population of 222 million and has the largest population in Africa. The population of people under 15 years of age is 91 million, while the population of people between 15 and 64 years is 124,565,242 (see figure 1). With the humongous population between 15 and 64, it is expected that an appreciable number of Nigerians will be admitted into tertiary institutions.

Figure 1: Nigeria 2023 population by age [1]

Unfortunately, this is not the case, the Nigeria University system can only admit less than 20 percent of those seeking admission to universities each year. In 2019, the total number of students in Nigerian Universities (both postgraduate and undergraduate) was 2 million [2]. This number is less than 5 percent of individuals between 15 and 64. With this number, one can argue that more than 80 percent of Nigerians willing to enroll in university programs cannot do so due to the lack of available slots. In 2022, the Joint Admissions and Matriculation board (JAMB) states that 1.75 million candidates register for the Universities Tertiary Matriculation Examination. Out of these number, 378,639 candidates scored 200 and above, 520,596 scored 190 and above, 704,991 scored 180 and above; 934,103 scored 170 and above; 1,192, 057 scored 160 and above (see Figure 2 for more) [3].

Figure 2: Number of candidates that sat for 2022 UTME examination [2]

The implication of these figures released by JAMB show that only very few students will gain admission into courses of their choice in 2022. A deeper analysis of the figures released by JAMB clearly puts the available slot for all undergraduate courses in Nigeria tertiary institutions at 420,000 (see figure 3) [4].

Figure 3: Number of available admission slot for 2022 UTME examination [2]

The challenge to gain admission in Nigeria tertiary institutions, have made parents and guidance see admission outside the shores of Nigeria. According to premium times [5], the number of Nigerians enrolled in US colleges rose to 14,000 in 2022 when compared to 12,000 in 2021. In the United Kingdom (UK), the number of Nigerians enrolled in colleges for the year 2020/2021 was 21,301 [6]. According to the association of Nigerian Students in Europe, over 3 million Nigerian students are currently enrolled in European Universities and Turkey [7]. Some of the reasons these students gave are unstable academic calendar and strikes by workers in the University. Although this may be a good reason, these reasons are far from the truth. If all the students studying abroad are to apply to Nigeria Universities, 90 percent of them will not be admitted due to the unavailability of slots. Young intelligent Nigerians that want to attend Universities in Nigeria cannot do so because of lack of available slots. In recent years, Nigerians who cannot afford education in developed countries but are willing to attain a degree are now turning to neighboring west African countries. For instance, in 2020 the Nigerian student account for the highest number of foreigners studying in Ghana. A total of 2960 Nigerian students are enrolled in Universities in Ghana [8]. In the republic of Benin, 90 percent of students in one of the Universities are Nigerians [9].

To be able to admit at least 50 percent of young Nigerians seeking admission to Universities in Nigeria, government and private individuals must do the following:

- 1) Create more private Universities with specialized functions: The National Universities Commission (NUC) should open the accreditation space for specialized private Universities. For instance, we can have smaller specialized Universities, say for example, University of management science, or social science and so on. With the creation of these smaller specialized Universities, more students can be employed
- 2) Upgrades of all Polytechnic/colleges and others to university status

3) Establishment of joint Universities with west African countries: To accommodate more intake of Nigerians, the Federal Government (FG) can enter into agreement with some neighboring country, to establish branches of some Nigeria Universities in those countries. For example, the University of Ibadan, can have a branch in Benin, or Togo then enter into agreement with the Government of Benin and Togo to have 50 percent of Nigerians admitted into such Universities. Finally, the more students the FG can get admitted into universities the better we educate our citizens.

Education is the passport to the future, for tomorrow belongs to those who prepare for it today.”—Malcolm X

GOD BLESS NIGERIA, NIGERIA SHALL RISE AGAIN, EDUCATION IS THE BUILDER

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